

Pilot Evaluation 6: Open Science

Final Version

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Summary

This Open Science pilot project was designed to simultaneously develop and experiment with two issues. First, discussing key policy issues in the framework of a European University alliance via a mechanism of formulating and debating bold hypotheses. Second, offering a fresh look at the idea of Open Science to further develop the concept of Open Science, and make it more understandable to researchers, professional staff members, and the public. In doing so, the pilot addressed the following transformation modules: foster Open Science and open access to scientific results and data, develop material for integration of science and society in curricula, and engage with multiple stakeholders for R&I decision-making at local, national, regional EU or global level.

In the first stage, the topic of the pilot project (i.e., the question of how Open Science should be understood) was chosen through an open discussion and consultations with various stakeholders (including Una.Resin WPs, Una Europa Future University Lab, clusters, Una.Resin Project Steering Committee). In the second stage, Una Europa's think tank, the Future University Lab, was entrusted with developing a concept note to provide a novel approach for understanding Open Science. In the third stage, the draft of the concept note was discussed internally (i.e., within the Una.Resin project) and updated accordingly. In the fourth stage, the final version of the concept note was adopted by the Future University Lab's Steering Committee, presented to the Una.Resin Project Steering Committee and the Una Europa Board of Directors, and distributed online among the Una Europa Community and beyond. In the fifth and final stage, the concept note was discussed in an online panel discussion, open to anyone interested.

In terms of important **outcomes**, it can be noted that this pilot project significantly contributed to increasing the understanding of the nature of Open Science practices and, in particular, how the openness of science constitutes an integral aspect of any rational scientific inquiry among the Una Europa community. Similarly, it showcased the usefulness of a methodology that uses bold (and often controversial) ideas to fuel broad discussions of policy-related issues. These outcomes may potentially lead to institutional change, both at the level of the Una Europa Alliance and in the broader context of the ERA. They influence understandings of Open Science and help researchers and professional staff members see how Open Science is intertwined with the quality of research, as well as with the social responsibility of the researcher.

As far as the **lessons learned** are concerned, it should be underlined that researchers and professional staff members tend to understand Open Science in a narrow way, making it difficult for them to see the real benefits it offers. Hence, a broader understanding of Open Science as a value may be beneficial to creating a more coherent view of science, one in which the quality of research is strengthened by both the individual and the public understanding of what science is. It is essential to reshape the academic culture to embrace a broader, more integrated understanding of Open Science, and illustrate how this can enhance the overall quality of research. Finally, environments that encourage critical

discussions of unconventional ideas should be encouraged so as to challenge the status quo and promote intellectual growth.

Objectives and aims of the pilot

The Open Science pilot project was designed to simultaneously develop and experiment with two issues. First, the goal was to test an innovative method for discussing a key policy issue in the framework of a European University Alliance via a mechanism for formulating and debating bold hypotheses. Secondly, we aimed to offer a fresh look at the very idea of Open Science in the hope of further developing the concept of Open Science and making it more understandable to researchers, professional staff members, and the public.

In light of the above, the Open Science pilot project addressed the following transformation modules:

- Foster Open Science and open access to scientific results and data (e.g., online open notebooks, OERs, open data, etc.): The pilot action directly addressed the importance of Open Science, its benefits, and the ways to effectively implement it, promoting a culture of openness and collaboration in scientific endeavours.
- Develop material for integration of science and society in curricula (e.g., covering STEM, public engagement, ethics, gender): By discussing the broader implications and benefits of Open Science for the public, the pilot action touched upon the relevance of integrating science within society, potentially paving the way for new curricular materials that bridge this gap.
- Engage with multiple stakeholders for R&I decision making at local, national, regional EU or global level: Through the open panel discussion, the initiative brought together academics, students, and professional staff, fostering a collaborative environment for decision-making and gathering insights from various stakeholders on Open Science.

The pilot action delved into the ambiguities surrounding the concept of Open Science within the European Research and Innovation Area. These ambiguities not only touch upon its definition but also highlight how Open Science is understood diversely across various research cultures. This diversity of understanding poses a challenge to effective cross-border and cross-sectoral research collaborations. Furthermore, the pilot project contributes to ongoing debates about Open Science emphasising its value and three key dimensions: accessibility, understandability, and sharing. By focusing on these dimensions, the project aligns with the EC's transformative measures to make research findings easily accessible and comprehensible to the broader society, and to foster the sharing of various research outputs. Furthermore, by identifying challenges and potential actions, the project offers pathways for institutions to adapt and transition towards a more inclusive and open research landscape. Emphasising Open Science as a value, rather than just a procedural requirement, indicates a broader understanding of the concept's significance.

The pilot project sought to initiate desired institutional change by:

- Developing gender equality plans/measures.
- Developing material for integration of science and society in curricula (e.g., covering STEM, public engagement, ethics, gender).
- Helping uphold human rights and high general ethical standards, by adoption, development and/or implementation of codes of conduct, ethical review, etc.

- Developing activities to anticipate the potential social, environmental, and economic impacts of research (e.g., risk assessment, threat assessment, foresight, impact assessment, gender analysis).
- Developing a social corporate responsibility dimension to foster responsible innovation.
- Helping develop R&I standards that enhance social responsibility, inclusiveness, and sustainability of R&I processes and products.
- Enlarging the scope of R&I activities by fostering informal science education (museums, science centres), promoting citizen science, and engaging civil society actors and citizens.
- Engaging with multiple stakeholders for R&I decision-making at local, national, and regional EU level or at the global level.
- Fostering Open Science and open access to scientific results and data (e.g., online open notebooks, OERs, open data, etc.).

To support the achievement of this change, the intended audiences of the pilot project are: universities in general, research performing organisation, public authorities, international organisations, researchers, businesses and industry engaged in R&D, citizens, and NGOs. With the beneficiaries of the pilot being: researchers, external users (academic and non-academic), citizens, other universities, and European University alliances.

Initial design and implementation of the pilot project

The pilot project was designed as a process leading to the formulation and discussion of bold hypotheses related to the concept of Open Science. These bold hypotheses provide a mean by which to interrogate understandings on Open Science, whilst providing inspiration and impulse for developing new tools and formats of cooperation to make science more open.

In the first stage, the topic of the pilot project (i.e., the question of how Open Science should be understood) was chosen via an open discussion and consultations with various stakeholders (WPs, Una Europa Future University Lab, clusters, the Project Steering Committee). In the second stage, Una Europa's think tank, the Future University Lab, was entrusted with developing a concept note, i.e., a document which provides a fresh look at the way Open Science is understood. The Future University Lab operates as a space for innovative, out-of-the-box thinking, where the task is to offer a new, often unexpected perspective on the discussed issue, question common assumptions, and enable a genuine creative process. The writing team appointed by the Future University Lab developed a concept note in which the understanding of Open Science as a value was presented and investigated in detail.

In the third stage, the draft of the concept note was discussed internally (i.e., within the Una.Resin Project), with various stakeholders (i.e., WP leaders, clusters - the Open Research cluster in particular), and with the Project Steering Committee (PSC) members. The inputs collected during this process were used to update the draft. In the fourth stage, the final version of the concept note was adopted by the Future University Lab's Steering Committee, presented to the Una.Resin PSC and Una Europa Board of Directors, and distributed online among the Una Europa Community and beyond. A dedicated communication channel was made available for the Una Europa community to share their views. In the fifth and final stage, the concept note was discussed during an online panel discussion, open to anyone interested.

Among the panellists, there were both experts involved in the Una.Resin project, as well as those who did not work on the concept note, or who were not even members of the Una Europa community.

The realisation of the pilot project encountered two major challenges. First, it was relatively difficult to organise a consultation process including so many stakeholders in the short timeframe available. Secondly, the consultations illustrated the immense difficulty of discussing ideas that go beyond established views and existing assumptions, with stakeholders having a tendency to go back to the well-known ways of conceptualising Open Science. However, with time and effort devoted to discussing the methodology behind the pilot project, the usefulness of the proposed approach was acknowledged by the stakeholders.

Outcomes and impact of the pilot project

The selection of the pilot project topic resulted from the conclusions of the Mapping Exercise of HR policies of Una Europa partner universities, which was conducted in the first phase of Una.Resin project. From the mapping exercise, it was noted that researchers have a narrow understanding of the nature and importance of Open Science, and that universities do not do enough to advance this understanding. The pilot project sought to address this, with the resulting outcomes including:

- The concept note “Open Science as a Value” developed by the Una Europa Future University Lab.
- A (recorded) online panel discussion on the value of Open Science
- An increased understanding among the Una Europa community of the nature of Open Science practices, and in particular how openness of science constitutes an integral aspect of any rational scientific inquiry.
- An increased understanding among the Una Europa community of the usefulness of the methodology which consists in providing bold (and often controversial) ideas to fuel broad discussions of policy-related issues.

The outcomes of the project may potentially lead to a degree of institutional change at the level of the Una Europa University Alliance, as well as in the broader context of the European Research Area. On the one hand, it may contribute to a broader understanding of Open Science, as well as help researchers and professional staff members to see how Open Science is intertwined with the quality of research and the social responsibility of the researcher. On the other hand, the outcomes of the pilot may inform the development of new tools and formats which will help expanding Open Science practices (e.g., the wording of documents/instructions pertaining to Open Science, inclusion of Open Science-related issues into the curricula, developing new, comprehensive communication formats pertaining to Open Science, etc.).

Sustainability of the pilot project

The insights and outcomes delivered through the pilot serve as the basis for further developments at three different levels:

- Discussion pertaining to the understanding of Open Science should continue, with the axiological dimension of the Open Science practices emphasised by the concept note in mind. Also, the format for generating discussions on the key policy-related issues

tested in the pilot should be replicated in relation to other key problems.

- The conclusions of the concept note should constitute a point of reference in developing policies, cooperation formats, and tools pertaining to Open Science developed within the Una Europa European University Alliance.
- The issues addressed in the concept note may be further discussed at the level of national and European policy-making.

Lessons learnt

The lessons learnt in this pilot project could be summarised as follows:

- **Conceptual expansion:** Researchers and professional staff members tend to understand Open Science in a narrow way, making it difficult for them to see the real benefits of Open Science.
- **Value integration:** A broader understanding of Open Science as a value may be beneficial to creating a more coherent view of science, one in which the quality of research is strengthened by both an individual and a public understanding of what science is.
- **Innovative dialogue:** It is difficult to discuss out-of-the-box ideas among researchers and professional staff members as they tend to understand the issues involved in an established, 'conventional' way.
- **Critical discourse:** It is beneficial to provide discussion mechanisms to discuss bold and controversial hypotheses to support with identifying limitations to existing ways of thinking.

The lessons learnt point to the necessity of reshaping academic culture to embrace a broader, more integrated understanding of Open Science, which can enhance the overall quality of research. Additionally, fostering environments that encourage critical discussions of unconventional ideas is essential for challenging the status quo and promoting intellectual growth.

Recommendations for the future

Future efforts should focus on cultivating ongoing discussions that reinforce Open Science as a core principle in policy-making and collaborative practices. It is also crucial to create platforms that encourage the exploration of unconventional ideas, challenge existing paradigms, and foster transformative developments in scientific policy.